

COVRIN WP2

SARS-CoV-2 Characterisation

D2.3.2

Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes

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GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	Pathology Toolbox
WP and Task	WP2 SARS-CoV-2 Characterisation / Task 2.3.2 Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes
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Due month of the report	M51
Actual submission month	M51
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 24/02/2022
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU See updated grant agreement
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

PATHOLOGY TOOLBOX

Pathology of laboratory animal models

A summary of the clinical, gross, histological and *in situ* virus detection results for SARS-CoV-2 animal models published by members of the consortium is provided in Table 1.

The commonly used mammalian species for SARS-CoV-2 modelling among the consortium are the ferret and golden Syrian hamster.

Ferrets experimentally inoculated SARS-CoV-2 generally do not produce clinical disease, except for a few incidental reports of lethargy and respiratory signs. The necropsy findings are unremarkable. At the microscopic level, rhinitis has been consistently noted and can be associated with virus infection *in situ* as corroborated with immunohistochemistry (IHC) and *in situ* hybridation (ISH), often early within the course of infection. The lungs however have occasional bronchiolitis and perivascular and peribronchiolar mononuclear cell cuffing. Viral detection in the lung is rare and has not been associated with histopathological lesion.

The golden Syrian hamster is highly susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection. Weight loss, increased temperature and reduction in activity occurs in the acute phase of infection spanning 4-10-days post-infection. Gross changes are limited to the lung, typically poorly collapsed lung lobes with multifocal red to brown discolouration. On histopathological examination, there is moderate to severe suppurative rhinitis, mild to moderate tracheitis and moderate to severe interstitial pneumonia with alveolar damage, associated with presence of virus antigens and RNA *in situ*.

Transgenic mice expressing human ACE2 proteins are also being used. Generally, these animals manifest disease as weight loss, encephalitis and mortality following SARS-CoV-2 inoculation. Although pathology read outs have not been included in the studies published by consortium members, experimental inoculation of transgenic mice can induce viral bronchointestinal pneumonia as described elsewhere [1].

To understand the risk of anthropozoonotic spill-over, fruit bats (*Rousettus aegyptiacus*) have also been experimentally inoculated with SARS-CoV-2. No clinical disease or gross pathology is reported. However, there is histopathologic evidence of minimal to mild rhinitis during early infection and associated with presence of virus antigens.

Experimental infection of other livestock species has been attempted, such as in the chicken and pig. These animals, however, do not exhibit productive infection nor clinical disease.

Table 1. Summary of clinical, gross, histological and *in situ* virus detection for SARS-CoV-2 animal model

Partner	Species	Clinical Findings	Gross Findings	Histological Findings	Viral IHC/ISH Findings	References
ANSES	Ferret	Lethargy was observed on 7- and 8-days post-infection (DPI) and occasionally snoring between 7-14 DPI. Temperature and weight remained stable.	n/a	Mild bronchiolitis at 2 DPI, with inflammatory cell infiltrates within the bronchiolar luminae, mostly neutrophils but some eosinophils, macrophages, and lymphocytes. Perivascular and peribronchiolar mononuclear cell cuffing (mainly mononuclear cells) at 4, 7 and 14 DPI. Small areas of consolidation with inflammatory infiltrates mainly macrophages and lymphocytes within the parenchyma.	One of the three animals killed at 2 DPI showed a few scattered cells with viral RNA detected in alveolar walls, not related to any histopathological lesion. No remarkable change was observed in the tonsil or the proximal trachea, with only a few scattered positive cells to viral RNA (ISH) in the trachea at 2 DPI not related to any histopathological lesion.	[2]
FLI	Ferret	No clinical signs or weight loss, body temperature remained normal.	No	At 4 DPI, viral antigen was associated with rhinitis, showing epithelial degeneration and necrosis, intraluminal cellular debris, and mild inflammation. A more severe rhinitis developed at 8 and 12 DPI. At 21 DPI, rhinitis was only slightly detectable or absent.	Viral antigen was detected in the nasal cavity at 4, 8, and 21 DPI in the nasal respiratory and olfactory epithelium as well as in the olfactory epithelium of the vomero-nasal organ, but not in the lung tissue. Selected immunohistochemistry results were confirmed by <i>in situ</i> hybridisation.	[3, 4]
APHA	Ferret	No weight loss or significant changes to temperatures.	No	Systematic histopathological examination of tissues revealed no marked changes. In the nasal turbinate, mucosal epithelial cells appeared to be uniform in shape and cilia were present, with rare presence of intra-epithelial neutrophils and apoptotic bodies.	Presence of viral antigens; nucleoprotein, only within the respiratory and olfactory epithelium of the nasal cavity. In the olfactory epithelium, the immunopositive cells had morphology suggestive of olfactory neuronal cells. Further evaluation using 5 gene ISH (RNAScope®) also confirmed this.	[5]
WBVR	Golden Syrian hamster	Maximum weight loss between 3 and 7 DPI. Activity reduction was observed in all juvenile hamsters after challenge and particularly low at 2 DPI but recovered by 9 DPI. Reduction in body temperature coincided with the substantially reduced activity in the juvenile hamsters.	Only in the lungs, characterized by poorly collapsed lungs with multifocal red to brown foci, often located around the bifurcation of the trachea	Moderate to severe suppurative rhinitis, characterized by the degeneration and necrosis of the epithelial layer and the accumulation of mainly heterophils in the epithelial layer and submucosa with exocytosis of heterophils in the nasal cavity. Mild to moderate tracheitis, characterised by loss of cilia on epithelial cells and epithelial cell degeneration. Increased inflammatory cells in the lamina propria and, to a lesser extent, in the epithelial layer. Moderate to severe interstitial pneumonia at 4, 7 and 10 DPI, characterized by the degeneration of alveolar walls, type II pneumocyte proliferation, vasculitis, influx of heterophils and haemorrhage. At 21 DPI, only mild histopathological lung lesions were present.	Viral antigen was found in the conchae, trachea, and lung (also in a tracheobronchial lymph node). The staining was observed predominantly in alveolar epithelial cells, bronchiolar epithelial cells and, to a lesser extent, in macrophages or desquamated alveolar epithelial cells	[6]
ANSES	Golden Syrian hamster	Temperature and weight remained stable. In hamsters, an average weight gain was observed in animals over time, and on average was reduced, although not significantly, in the inoculated group compared to uninfected controls.	n/a	Damage of the olfactory epithelium (OE) in infected animals as early as 2 DPI. The nasal cavity lumen was filled with cellular aggregates and most of the OE was strongly disorganized. In the most affected OE zones, axon bundles from the olfactory sensory neurons (SN) under the OE were almost in direct contact with the environment. Most of the OE had disappeared at 4 DPI, after which point it started to recover but had not reached pre-infection thickness at 14 DPI. SNs lost most of their cilia as early as 2 DPI In the trachea, mild inflammatory infiltration of the epithelium was observed with minimal to mild epithelial necrosis at 2, 4 and 7 DPI. Inflammatory infiltration was observed in the lung from 2 to 7 DPI, with the presence of macrophages, lymphocytes and neutrophils surrounding airways and within the alveolar walls.	Large amount of viral RNA detected by ISH, mostly at 2 and 4 DPI, and at much lower level at 7 DPI in the lung. The viral RNA positive area in the lung diminished at day 5 and coincided with inflammatory infiltrates. No viral RNA detected at 10 and 14 DPI. Viral RNA was very abundant within the tracheal epithelial cells at 2 DPI and decreased from 4 DPI with a complete absence from 7 DPI onwards. Using multi-labelling approach, SARS-CoV-2 is evident to be infecting sustentacular cells but not OSN.	[2, 7, 8]
FLI	Golden Syrian hamster	Weight loss	n/a	n/a	n/a	[3]
FLI	Transgenic hACE2 mice	Weight loss, mortality, encephalitis	n/a	n/a	n/a	[3, 9]
FLI	Fruit bat	No clinical signs, fever, bodyweight loss, nor mortality	No	Minimal to mild rhinitis at 4 DPI, with epithelial necrosis, oedema, infiltrating lymphocytes and neutrophils, and intraluminal cellular debris. Moderate rhinitis was detected at 8 and 12 DPI, and to a milder extent at 21 DPI, despite lacking viral antigens	Viral antigen detection, restricted to foci in the nasal respiratory epithelium and single cells of the non-respiratory epithelium, were confirmed ISH. Despite the detection of viral RNA by RT-qPCR, no viral antigen was detectable in the lung tissue.	[4]
FLI	Pig	No clinical signs, fever, bodyweight loss	No	Not performed	n/a	[4]
FLI	Chicken	No clinical signs, fever, bodyweight loss	No	Not performed	n/a	[4]

n/a = not available

Investigative Toolboxes

Detection of viral proteins and RNA

To enable the provision of specific histopathology findings in consideration of virus infection *in situ*, IHC and *in situ* hybridisation (RNAScope®) targeting viral antigens and RNA have been deployed (Table 2).

Nucleoprotein antigen is often the target of choice for IHC and can be successfully detected following heat-mediated pH6 or enzymatic protease antigen retrieval. IHC targeting the spike protein is only used by one institute. ISH (RNAScope®) has also been used, with probes against spike or nucleoprotein described.

Apart from the conventional two-dimensional approach on visualising virus on tissue sections, a volumetric three-dimensional immunofluorescent imaging using tissue optical clearing and light sheet microscopy have been reported for ferret model. This advance imaging technique can provide greater spatial resolution and detailed quantification of infection foci [10].

Detection of host cell receptor protein

ACE2 is a host protein that mediates binding of the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 to facilitate virus entry into target host cell. Two participating institutes have used the same antibody and visualisation method to evaluate ACE2 in animal tissues. This technique has been applied to evaluate the spatial distribution of ACE2 proteins in tissues including companion animals, livestock, and zoological animals [11]. Other animal species are also currently being investigated by partnering institutes within COVRIN to broaden the knowledge on ACE2 receptor distribution in tissues.

Table 2. Methods for visualising virus antigen and RNA and host receptor in tissues

Partner	Antigen raised	Clonality	Species Raised	Manufacturer, product identifier	Antibody Dilution Ratio	Antigen Retrieval Method				Publication
						Heat pH6	Heat pH9	Proteinase/Protease	Others Methods	
Virus Antigen Detection										
APHA	SARS-CoV spike 1 subunit protein	IgG, monoclonal	Rabbit	Sinobiological, 40150-R007	1/800		Yes			[5]
APHA	SARS-CoV nucleocapsid	IgG, polyclonal	Rabbit	Sinobiological, 40163-T62	1/1000	Yes		Yes		[5]
WBVR	SARS-CoV nucleocapsid	Polyclonal	Rabbit	Sinobiological, 40163-T62	1/2500	Yes				[12]
SVA	SARS-CoV nucleocapsid	IgG, polyclonal	Rabbit	Sinobiological	1/1000			Yes		
FLI	SARS-CoV nucleocapsid	IgG, polyclonal	Rabbit	Rockland Immunochemicals # 200-401-A50	1/3000	Yes				
FLI	SARS-CoV nucleocapsid	IgG, polyclonal	Rabbit	Novus Biologicals,, # NB100-56576	1/200	Yes				[13]
FLI	SARS-CoV-1 nucleocapsid	IgG, polyclonal	Rabbit	Antikörper online/ Rockville, ABIN6952544	1/500				Tissue Optical Clearing	
FLI	SARS-CoV-2 nucleocapsid	IgG1, monoclonal	Mouse	Sinobiological, 40143-MM05	1/400				Tissue Optical Clearing	
FLI	SARS-CoV-1 nucleocapsid	IgG, polyclonal	Rabbit	Novus Biologicals, NB100-56576	1/250				Tissue Optical Clearing	[10]
FLI	SARS-CoV-1 nucleocapsid	IgG, monoclonal	Mouse	AB_2833160	1/5				Tissue Optical Clearing	[10]
FLI	SARS-CoV-1 nucleocapsid	IgG, monoclonal	Mouse	AB_2833162	1/5				Tissue Optical Clearing	[10]
Virus RNA Detection										
APHA	SARS-CoV-2 spike	n/a	n/a	V-nCoV2019-5, catalogue no. 848569	Neat				Per RNAScope® instruction	[5]
FLI	SARS-CoV-2 NSP	n/a	n/a	SARS-CoV-2 NSP	Neat				Per RNAScope® instruction	[4]
Host Receptor Detection										
APHA	ACE2	Polyclonal	Rabbit	Abcam, ab15348	1/1000	Yes				[11]
FLI	ACE2	Polyclonal	Rabbit	Abcam, ab15348	1/1000	Yes				

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